

Assessing Teacher Competence and Learners' Performance in Alternative Learning System: A case study of Northern Aurora

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ABSTRACT:

The purpose of this study is to find out the teachers' competence and learners' performance in the Alternative Learning System in Northern Aurora for the calendar year 2025. A descriptive survey method was used in this study. The study's respondents were all DepEd permanent teachers of the Bureau of Alternative Learning System in Northern Aurora province and officially teaching secondary learners in the different Community Learning Centers (CLCs) or schools implementing the Alternative Learning System Accreditation and Equivalency Test (A&E) for CY 2025. The respondents of the research covered two groups, namely (1) learner-respondents who were ALS learners and (2) teacher-respondents who were the Community ALS Implementers (CAIs), composed of District ALS Coordinators (DALSCs) who were assigned to the District Learning Center and mobile teachers (MTs) who were assigned to the Community Learning Center in the far-flung barangays. There were 6 Community ALS Implementers and 195 learner-respondents in this study. Regression correlation was used to determine the significant relationship between the teachers' profiles related to their competence, the learners' profiles between their performance in the Competency-Based Examination, and the teachers' competence regarding the Competency-Based Examination. The majority of the respondents were males who outnumbered the females. With regards to the educational attainment of the respondents, the majority of respondents had master's degrees, and half of the respondents had 6–10 years of teaching experience in the ALS. And, most of the respondents receive a salary of ₱ 25,000.00 to ₱ 35,000.00 a month. Predominantly, the learner-respondents were aged 15 to 24, and more than half of the respondents were male. The majority of the learner-respondents were single, and most of them resided near the vicinity of the Community Learning Center, having a distance of between 101 to 500 meters. Results of the study revealed that the teaching competence of the respondents was very high, with a computed mean score of 4.37, with verbal interpretation of "very competent." The demographic profile of teachers shows that it was not significant to the teaching competence of the respondents. The majority of the learners had passed the competency-based assessment, with a computed weighted mean of 75.47. The learners' sex, age, and civil status were found to have no significant relationship with the competency-based examination, while the distance of the residence from the community learning center revealed a highly significant one. The result implies that the teacher's competence has no relationship to the learner's performance in the competency-based examination. Some of the recommendations to enrich the instructional program were as follows: More satellite Community Learning Centers should be established to reach out to other out-of-school youths in every barangay, and Community ALS Implementers should be appointed to look after the welfare of the learners.

Keywords— Alternative Learning System, Teacher Competence, Learner's Performance, Accreditation, and Equivalency Test

INTRODUCTION

Global Education found that 234 million school-aged children and adolescents in 60 countries are affected by crises and need help getting adequate education. Since 2021, 6 million more children have dropped out of school, reaching 250 million. A quarter of a billion children and adolescents are not in school despite decades of progress and international accords (Global Education, 2025). Thus, the Department of Education's Alternative Learning System's (ALS) Accreditation and Equivalency (A&E) is essential to achieving the Basic Education (BEDP) 2030 objective of "Universal Coverage of Out-of-School Young People and Older People in the Provision of Basic Education" in the Philippines. This goal is to help all unenrolled students get basic education. Alternative learning systems target out-of-school youth and adults who didn't finish basic education. After working as a district ALS coordinator in Dinalungan, Aurora, one of Northern Aurora's districts, the researcher transferred to Aurora State College of Technology. The researcher was inspired by his previous ALS colleagues who served out-of-school adolescents in remote places. Mobile Teachers (MTs) of Casiguran who interacted with indigenous citizens, particularly in San Ildefonso, Dumaguipo, and other remote barangays, felt self-fulfilled and self-worth, which inspired the researcher to investigate the ALS A&E program for the indigenous community. Mobile Teachers (MTs) of Casiguran told the researcher stories that inspired him. In Dinalungan, where the researcher was District ALS Coordinator, certain barangays implemented the program. The researcher was inspired to serve out-of-school youth (OSY) in Barangays Paleg, Mapalad, and Ditawini. Altruism, according to Ayn Rand, is putting others first. The researcher, who is a college instructor, has consistently tried to embody Auguste Comte's principle of altruism by helping those in need of education. Individual development and advancement depend on education. Improving a country's education will help every Filipino reach their full potential and use their skills for the nation. ALS, on the other hand, addresses Filipinos' essential needs: reading, writing, math, communication, life profession skills, self-awareness, and digital competency. ALS Philippines is forward-looking to expand the program and meet Filipinos' requirements, and capturing the character of ALS in the country yields various results. Fernandez (2013) suggested conducting a similar study in other regions with a focus on A&E exam performance. The Alternative Learning System is centered in northern Aurora's Dinalungan, Casiguran, and Dilasag districts. The Community Learning Centers (CLCs) in Dilasag, Dinalungan, Casiguran, and each barangay serve out-of-school youth and adults who want to finish junior high school through the ALS A&E program. This study suggests that Alternative Learning System teachers who focus on student success and skill-based examinations may improve Accreditation and Equivalency Test scores in future years.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE:

(A) Review of Literature Related to Teacher Competence

Professor William Sanders of the University of Tennessee makes a persuasive case that teacher influence is the biggest element affecting student academic gain. Teachers need them to learn more. According to a study, the readiness of teachers is crucial because they are dealing with diverse students with different characteristics and motivations. Teachers, particularly those in remote barangays, must enhance their educational qualifications, and the only way to achieve those goals is by enrolling in a higher education

program. Alternative Learning System students rely solely on the skills and wisdom of the teacher. **(2021, Pablo).**

Stabback (2016) said students need a good teacher who will teach them well. Educational institutions should research teacher competencies to build curricula and programs. Some studies suggest that the effectiveness of teachers' instruction varies with the duration of their teaching experience, according to various studies. This effect is likely to be most noticeable in the first five years of a teacher's career, but it continues to rise in the second and third decades **(Podolsky and Kini, 2019)**. Even though experience significantly raises a teacher's quality of instruction, continuing education programs, like going to higher education, are necessary to improve a teacher's teaching abilities. Both seasoned and inexperienced teachers require strong institutional support to improve their teaching abilities and, eventually, student outcomes **(Darling-Hammond, 2017)**.

Another significant concept regarding teacher competence is that teacher pay substantially impacts teacher performance. **Ahmed (2024)** asserted that higher teacher salaries correlate with increased productivity and performance among educators. Moreover, salary is not a determinant of excellence or development; rather, it is the teacher's passion for teaching that fosters effectiveness. Teachers often cite diverse attributes that contribute to a great educator, including being nurturing, knowledgeable, or an effective communicator, as well as being demanding and encouraging hard work. This dedication stems from their love for the profession, even in the absence of adequate compensation. Not all teachers who exhibit affection or possess expertise in their subject field are necessarily effective **(Richwine, 2011)**.

(B) Review of Literature related to Learner Performance

A study on lifelong learning found that adult learners were doing well academically, taking advantage of opportunities to display their ability, actively participating in their known subject matter, and comparing their work to others to show their superiority. They aim to establish themselves as the most knowledgeable and experienced students in the class, actively participating, prepared to learn, and diligently striving for improved outcomes. In large groups of students who began school together, their preparedness for the A&E exam may affect the results, rather than their age or length of education **(Tan, 2019)**.

In the classroom, **Han (2012)** stresses gender inequalities. Boys are less driven than girls because of their differences and interests, unless the contents interest them. Many individuals now realize that psychological differences between the sexes affect how they think, communicate, and act. These differences are evident in the playground, classroom, family, and workplace. Since gender is a critical factor in learning and professional development, teachers should consider their beliefs and practices to account for gender differences to better support all students' social competence.

Fernandez (2013) found that the learners' civil status does not have any impact on their performance in alternative learning systems. Single students may perform better in the A&E test than married learners for several reasons: married learners often have many priorities related to their work and family, which may affect their test results; however, research suggests that both single and married learners can perform well in the A&E test.

Residential distance from the CLC affects academic attainment and school patronage. The accessibility and travel distance from school for ALS secondary students affects their economic, home, and school participation. Education International Research found that long school commutes harm pupils' health and academic performance. Long distances cause morning weariness, which lowers a student's attentiveness,

according to research. Students lose focus in class due to long commutes. Many pupils arrive at school sweating, stressed, and exhausted, which hurts their academic performance (**Bashaiza, 2016**).

Materials and Method

A survey system was used in this exploratory paper. The study was conducted in the northern part of Aurora Province, which includes the municipalities of Dinalungan, Dilasag, and Casiguran. For this study, the total number of teachers at the time of the study was 6, while the total number of learners, totaling 195, is based on the actual number of learners who were regular attendees of each ALS implementer from their respective community learning centers. We limited the respondents to junior high school secondary-level learners.

Sampling-

In this study, the ALS implementers selected were those implementing the Accreditation and Equivalency program for CY 2025, and the ALS learners selected through random sampling were those enrolled in the program during CY 2025.

Tool-

A self-designed tool assessed the ALS implementer's expertise and the student's Alternative Learning System performance. The ALS Individual Performance Commitment Review (IPCRF) served as the model for teacher questionnaires, each of which had two components. In part 1, the CAIs completed a personal information sheet that asked respondents for their name, sex, education, years of ALS teaching experience, and salary. Part 2 covered teacher competence with 18 questions. Teachers were asked about their subject knowledge, methodical lesson presentation, discussion of current issues and their relationship to current events, how they answer questions, how they pique students' interest, how they encourage critical thinking, how they use visual aids and strategies in the classroom, how they assess their communication skills, how they evaluate students' performance, and how quickly they visit the centers. The item was stated in a five-point Likert-type scale in which the respondents indicated their chosen answer by placing a check mark in the space provided by the respondents for every item given.

Statistical Analysis-

SPSS was used for data analysis and interpretation, and manual computation was done for rechecking. Teacher and student sociodemographic profiles were described using frequencies and percentages for questions 1 and 2. To assess instructor competence, weighted mean was calculated for question 3. For question 4, regression correlation (standard coefficient), Spearman's rho, and Pearson's r were used to assess if teacher-respondent socio-demographic profile and teacher competence are related. In question 5, weighted mean, percentage, and frequency distribution determined the learner's CBE performance. Regression and correlation (standard coefficient), Pearson's r, and Spearman's rho were used to establish if the socio-demographic profile and CBE performance are related in question 6. Regression Correlation was utilized to investigate if teacher competence affects CBE performance in question 7.

The following scale was used for verbal interpretation of the teacher's competence

5	Very Competent (VC)	Demonstrates very high degree of success in performing instructional and other duties in teaching.
4	Competent (C)	Manifest a high degree of success in performing instructional and other duties in teaching.
3	Moderately Competent (MC)	Demonstrates success in performing Instructional and other duties in teaching.
2	Slightly Competent (SC)	Reveals low degree in performing Instructional and other duties in teaching.
1	Not Competent (NC)	Shows very low degree of success in performing Instructional and other duties in teaching.

The researcher used a competency-based examination to assess learner competency in the 6 learning strands of Accreditation and Equivalency core modules: English and Filipino communication skills, scientific literacy, critical thinking, arithmetic and problem-solving skills, life and career competencies, self and societal knowledge, and digital literacy or citizenship. Experts validated the tool, and the author conducted pilot research with 20 ALS A&E students to assess its dependability. The A&E program has one set of CBE questions for secondary students.

RESULT & DISCUSSION

Table 2 shows the sex of the respondents. There were 4 (67 %) male teachers, while 2 (33%) were female. Females today who are inclined to the teaching profession are increasing in number.

Sex	Frequency	Percentage%
Male	4	66
Female	2	33
Total	6	100

As regards the case of the Alternative Learning System in Northern Aurora, the number of male teachers was slightly higher than females. The slight difference could be explained by the association that male teachers enjoy reaching far-flung barangays.

Educational Attainment

Table 3 shows the educational attainment of the respondents. There were 5 (83%) teachers with master’s degrees/units and only one (17%) teacher with a doctorate. It implies that most of the respondents are continuing their master's studies for their personal and professional development.

Educational attainment	Frequency	Percentage
With Masteral Units	5	83
Master’s degree	0	0
With Doctoral Unit	1	17
PhD	0	0
Total	6	100

This data connotes that most of the Alternative Learning System teachers in Northern Aurora are striving hard to continue to grow to work hard on the andragogy aspect of teaching.

Years of Teaching Experience in ALS

Table 4 shows the work experience of the respondents. There was 1 (17%) teacher who had been teaching for 1 to 5 years, 3 (50 %) for 6–10 years, and 2 (33%) for 11 to 15 years. The computed mean is 8.33 with a standard deviation of 2.62 years.

Years of teaching experience	Frequency	Percentage
1-5	1	17
6-10	3	50
11-15	2	33
Total	6	100

Mean = 8.33

Standard Deviation = 2.62

It implies that the majority of the respondents have been working in the field of education for more than six years. This shows they have more knowledge, planning, and teaching methods to meet each student's unique needs.

Salary of Teachers

Table 5 shows the salary of the respondents. There were 5 (83%) teachers who had a salary of ₱ 25,000.00 to ₱ 35,000.00; none (0 %) received ₱ 36,000.00 to ₱46,000.00, while 1 (17%) had a salary of ₱ 47,000 to ₱ 57,000.00.

Salary of Teachers	Frequency	Percentage
₱ 25,000.00 to ₱ 35,000.00	5	83
₱ 36,000.00 to ₱ 46,000.00	0	0
₱ 47,000.00 to ₱ 57,000.00	1	17
Total	6	100

Mean = 31,833

Standard Deviation = 17029.99

The computed mean was 31,833 with a standard deviation of 17029.99. It implies that most of the respondents have a salary of ₱ 25,000.00 to ₱ 35,000.00 thousand, referring to their gross monthly income as a Teacher 1 to Teacher III DepEd salary wage position. The table also shows that only 1 teacher had a salary of ₱ 47,000.00 to ₱ 57,000.00 thousand for her master teacher position.

Profile of the Learners

The profile of learners includes age, sex, civil status, and distance of residence from the Community Learning Center.

Table 6 shows the ages of the respondents. There were 153(78. %) learners aged 15 to 24 years old, 35 (18 %) were in their mid-30s, aged 25 to 34, while 3 (2 %) were in the middle age of 35 to 44 years old, while 4 (2 %) were in the 45 and above years of age. The computed mean was 21.82 with a standard deviation of 6.51 years.

Age	Frequency	Percentage
15-24	153	78
25-34	35	18
35-44	3	2
45 and above	4	2
Total	195	100

Mean = 21.82

Standard Deviation = 6.51

This result implies that most of the early teens and the young adults are still encouraged to pursue education in order for them to gain knowledge and a diploma, which is necessary to continue their studies in higher education or in finding jobs. Age is not required as long as the learners reach the age of 15 and are high school dropouts, and anyone can take the ALS A&E test. Table 5 shows that some of the learners were aged 45 and above. Although minimal in number, these old learners still are willing to finish their secondary education.

Sex

Table 7 shows the sex of the respondents. There were 105 (54 %) male learners, while 90 (46%) were females. This means that more than half of the male learners responded in the program to at least try to finish their secondary education.

Sex	Frequency	Percentage%
Male	105	54
Female	90	46
Total	195	100

Civil Status

Table 8 shows the civil status of the respondents. There were 151 (77 %) learners who were single, while 44 (23 %) were married.

Civil Status of learners	Frequency	Percentage%
Single	151	77
Married	44	23
Total	195	100

The findings reveal that most of the learner respondents were single, predominantly comprising individuals who were either unemployed or underemployed. This group includes both young individuals and adults who are not currently enrolled in educational institutions, having either exited or discontinued their participation in primary and secondary schooling. The remaining 23% consisted of married individuals from various industries, homemakers, domestic workers, drivers, and laborers. Most of the target learners are impoverished, primarily hailing from marginalized, underprivileged, and underserved communities. The reduced number of married students can be explained by their concurrent commitments to both education and employment, as they endeavor to fulfill their family's requirements.

Distance of Residence from the Community Learning Center

Table 9 shows the distance of residence of the respondents from the Community Learning Center. There were 34 (17 %) learners whose residence had the distance of 100 meters and below from their respective Community Learning Centers, 114 (58 %) had the distance of 101 to 500 meters, while 8 (4 %) needed to encounter the distance of 501 meters to 1000 meters, while 39 (20%) lived at a distance of 1001 meters and above.

Distance	Frequency	Percentage %
100 meter and below	34	17
101 meters to 500 meters	114	58
501 meters to 1000 meter	8	4
1001 meter and above	39	20
Total	195	100

This finding indicates that most learners live in close proximity to the Community Learning Center, allowing them the option to walk or take a ride to access the facility. A number of the learners were located at a considerable distance from the Community Learning Center, requiring half an hour or more to arrive at the location. Students traveling from a distance to the Community Learning Center occasionally arrive late due to the lengthy commute. This impacts their attendance and influences their academic performance. The accessibility and the distance from school to the Community Learning Centers significantly impact the learners' engagement in economic activities, household responsibilities, and their school attendance. The greater the duration of the commute to school, the more challenging it becomes for

the student to balance work and attendance. Specifically, minimizing the travel time to school appears to be especially beneficial for households with lower income levels.

Teachers' Competence

Table 10 shows the instructional competence of the teacher, which obtained an overall weighted mean of 4.37 with a description of "very competent." Teachers' knowledge of the subject matter, methodical presentation of the lesson, discussion of current issues and their relationship to current events, how they answer questions, how they pique students' interest, how they encourage critical thinking in students, how they use various visual aids and strategies in the classroom, how they assess their communication skills, how they evaluate students' performance, how quickly they visit the centers, and their behavior and emotional maturity were all considered components of the teacher respondents' competence. Table 10 shows the instructional competence of the teacher, which obtained an overall weighted mean of 4.37 with a description of "very competent."

	Performance Indicator	WM	Description
1	Provide a thorough explanation of the lesson's objectives at the start of each period.	4.64	VC
2	Prepare prescribed session guides and appropriate instructional materials.	4.42	VC
3	Exhibits expertise in the subject matter.	4.52	VC
4	Systematically convey subject matter by adhering to the course outline.	4.43	VC
5	The content is consistent with the most recent developments, which are pertinent to the subject matter.	4.39	VC
6	Use various methods, teaching tools, and strategies when delivering the lesson.	4.36	VC
7	Respond effectively to learner comments and suggestions.	4.37	VC
8	Had a positive attitude toward assisting learners in understanding course material.	4.33	VC
9	Employ the technique of inquiry to cultivate advanced cognitive processes.	4.32	VC
10	Ensures learners' participation.	4.33	VC
11	Addresses individual differences	4.41	VC
12	The educational requirements of learners are assessed through the individual learning agreement.	4.23	VC
13	Monitor and evaluate the learner's learning process.	4.25	VC

14	Evaluates the lesson to ascertain the intended results within the allocated time management and learning environment.	4.24	VC
15	Translate ALS learning materials and other materials into the local language of the learners or community as the need arises.	4.58	VC
16	Develop strategies and execute them to maintain the progress of learners in the ALS program.	4.25	VC
17	Conduct an action research activity to improve the teaching and learning process.	4.30	VC
18	Report in the assigned Community Learning Center/ALS Center on time.	4.22	VC
OVERALL WEIGHTED MEAN		4.37	VC

Likert scale:

4.21 – 5.00 =	Very Competent (VC)	3.41 – 4.20 =	Competent(C)
2.66 – 3.40 =	Moderately Competent (MC)	1.81 – 2.60 =	Slightly Competent (SC)
1 – 1.80 =	Not Competent (NC)		

The scores achieved by the teacher-respondents in terms of competence ranged from 4.22 to 4.64, indicating a level of very competent performance in several areas, including mastery of the subject matter, the formulation of questions to elucidate lessons, the utilization of diverse teaching aids, the implementation of various teaching strategies, and the provision of challenging tasks relevant to real-life situations. This outcome suggests that the teacher respondents exhibited a significant level of commitment to the program's implementation. Educators are particularly attentive to articulating the lesson objectives with clarity at the beginning of each session, a practice essential for facilitating the learning process and fostering the engagement of all students. It has been demonstrated that the translation of ALS learning materials and other resources into the local language of the learners or community, as necessary, holds considerable importance. The evidence indicates that educators adhere closely to directives related to the local translation of content. Such behavior serves to guarantee the engagement of learners, indicating that comprehension of the lesson must be conveyed in a manner that resonates with their linguistic framework.

Relationship between the Socio-demographic Profile and Teachers’ Competence among Teacher-Respondents.

Table 11 illustrates the noteworthy connection between the socio-demographic profile and competence among the teacher respondents. The analysis reveals that the demographic profile of the teacher respondents, including gender, salary, educational qualifications, and years of experience in the Alternative Learning System, did not show a significant correlation with their teaching competence. The computed regression correlation (Pearson r) values were 0.725, 0.505, 0.504, and 0.836, respectively.

Teacher’s Profile	Test Value	P. value
Sex	.352 ^{ns}	.725
Salary	.668 ^{ns}	.505
Educational Attainment	-.670 ^{ns}	.504
Years in teaching in ALS	-.208 ^{ns}	.836

^{ns} - not significant

The result shows that the respondents' demographic profile is not significantly correlated with their teaching expertise. Specifically, it indicates that the teaching abilities of a teacher are unaffected by factors such as gender, salary, educational level, or number of years spent in the profession. The research was supported by Turk and Kormaz (2022); teachers' profiles are not always directly correlated; instead, teaching competence encompasses a wide range of skills, including pedagogical knowledge, classroom management, and interpersonal skills. These competencies are not solely determined by formal qualifications or years of experience. For instance, a teacher with a lower level of formal education might possess exceptional communication skills and emotional intelligence, which are crucial for effective teaching. Furthermore, a good educator is regarded as a social and moral model, and as such, they carry with them a certain degree of status and respectability that needs to be fostered. The person in question is not just practicing a profession; they are out there to shape the character of the future citizens.

Learners' Performance in the Competency-Based Examination

The results of the Competency-Based Examination are presented in Table 12. This assessment was intended to evaluate the proficiency level of learners in the six learning strands encompassed in the core modules of the Accreditation and Equivalency Test. The learning components encompass communication skills in English and Filipino, scientific literacy, critical thinking, arithmetic and problem-solving abilities, life and career competencies, self and societal knowledge, and digital literacy or citizenship. The test is composed of 20 items; the respondent's score is reflected in the table with the corresponding percentage. The graph shows that out of 195 respondents, 113 (58%) got the highest score in the CBE. There were 147 (75%) respondents who passed the test, while 48 (25%) respondents failed. The computed mean was 75.47 with a standard deviation of 14.35.

CBE Score	Frequency	Percentage
18-20	30	15
15-17	113	58
12-14	28	15
9-11	14	7
6-8	10	5
Total	195	100

Figure 3. Graph showing learner’s performance in Competency Based Examination

It implies that the majority of the learners passed the competency-based examination. This means that the test that was administered is an effective design to meet the desired outcome. An effective design of a competency-based examination encompasses several characteristics: it commences with clearly articulated learning outcomes, proceeds with an analysis of how to structure learning activities to achieve these outcomes, and subsequently aligns competencies with content, incorporating analytics to monitor performance. Additionally, the examination's reliability, validity, objectivity, and usability are duly considered. The usability of the test is a crucial attribute of measurement equipment, as practical issues of the evaluation tool must not be overlooked. The assessment must possess practical significance in terms of time, cost-efficiency, and management. This characteristic may be referred to as usability. On the other hand, some of the learners failed with a corresponding average score of 30-70%, meaning they cannot fully understand the exam or they did not prepare for the test, because the CBE was administered before the Alternative Learning System A&E test, so some of the learners have not yet reviewed for the exam. Also, some of the learners reside far from the Community Learning Center, so they do not have the privilege of attending the review regularly.

Relationship between the Socio-demographic Profile and Learners-Performance in the Competency Based Examination

Table 13 demonstrates the notable correlation between the socio-demographic profiles of the learner-respondents and their outcomes in the competency-based examination. The demographic profile of learners is detailed, including aspects such as sex, age, civil status, and the distance of their residence from the Community Learning Center, all of which are associated with the Competency-Based Examination. The analysis revealed that there is no substantial relationship between learners' performance and sex, as evidenced by a regression correlation of 0.440. The correlation for age was determined to be 0.306, whereas civil status exhibited a correlation of 0.64. The analysis indicated that the distance of the residence from the Community Learning Center significantly influenced the learner’s performance in the competency-based examination, resulting in a calculated regression correlation of 0.003.

Learners profile	Frequency	Percentage
Sex	.773 ^{ns}	.440
Age	1.026 ^{ns}	.306
Civil Status	1.861 ^{ns}	.064
Distance of the residence from the Community Learning Center	2.962**	.003

^{ns} - not significant **-highly significant

The result implies that learners who reside far from the Community Learning Center cannot perform well in the competency-based examination. Access to and proximity to the community learning center influence learners' participation in economic activities, household chores, and school attendance. For this reason, it was concluded that the proximity to the community learning center plays a highly significant role. This result implied that learners' academic performance, particularly in the competency-based examination, correlates with their place of residence. Bashaiza (2016) supported the result, citing research indicating that lengthy commutes to school negatively impact students' health and educational achievement levels. He further stated that long distances induce fatigue at the start of the day, which adversely affects a learner's concentration. The extended commutes students make to school disrupt their concentration in class. Many students arrive at school in a state of physical and psychological distress, characterized by sweating, stress, and exhaustion, which negatively impacts their academic performance.

Relationship between Teachers' Competence and Learners' Performance in the Competency Based Examination

Table 14 demonstrated the significant relationship between teacher competence and learner performance in the competency-based examination. This examination includes six educational strands: communication abilities in English and Filipino, scientific understanding and critical thinking, mathematical proficiency and problem-solving capabilities, life and career competencies, self and societal awareness, and digital literacy or citizenship. The findings indicate that teacher competence does not significantly impact learners' performance in the competency-based examination, with a computed regression correlation of 0.147.

Teacher Competence	Test Value	P. Value
Teacher	1.457 ^{ns}	.147

^{ns} - not significant

This result implies that a teacher's competence has no relationship to the learners' performance in the competency-based examination. Therefore, it is evidence proving that teacher competence across the six learning strands of the Competency Based Examination and the learner's performance in the Competency Based Examination were the same. The learner's capacity to succeed in the test is not solely dependent on the teachers; rather, teachers serve as one of the resources to assist learners in navigating the test, while the learner must actively engage in the process to reach their objectives. Students' lack of motivation or interest can hinder even the most skilled teacher's ability to enhance performance. Personal interest, intrinsic motivation, and material relevance significantly influence learning outcomes. Multiple students interviewed by the researcher supported this finding. They prioritize job security over educational attainment, irrespective of their completion of schooling. The situation affects many students, especially those from impoverished and Indigenous backgrounds, and their desire and motivation significantly

influence their academic pursuits (Flemings & Mills, 1992). The observation that teachers' competence does not significantly influence learners' performance in the CBE can be explained by the following reasons: Numerous community learning centers present accessibility challenges for CAIs due to their geographical location and structural complexity, resulting in infrequent in-person interactions between teachers and learners. The rates of student absenteeism are high. A mobile teacher recounted a day at a community learning center characterized by a limited number of learners. Community learning centers in Northern Aurora are primarily constructed using lightweight materials, repurposing unoccupied government facilities such as day care centers or utilizing abandoned structures like the former Barangay Hall, as well as learners' residences. The absence of school facilities in remote barangays necessitates the use of tree shade as informal learning centers for the community. Leitwood and Jantzi (2007) asserted that student performance is contingent upon school facilities, resources, and support. Insufficient resources can constrain even the most effective educators. A significant number of ALS learners engage in their studies via their guardians rather than participating in community ALS sessions. Fan & Chen (2001) assert that parental participation enhances adolescents' academic achievement, a notion so intuitively compelling that it has been regarded by society and educators as a fundamental element of numerous educational reforms. Parental involvement in a student's education can significantly influence academic achievement. Students with more engaged parents achieve superior outcomes, irrespective of teacher quality.

Conclusion:

A Based on the summary of findings, the following conclusions were drawn: The respondents predominantly consisted of male teachers, with a significant number possessing master's degrees; half of them reported having teaching experience between 6 to 10 years. Most participants indicated that their monthly earnings fell between ₱25,000.00 to ₱35,000.00. The predominant age group among the learner-respondents was 15 to 24 years, with more than half identifying as male. A significant portion of the learner respondents identified as single, with many residing in close proximity to the Community Learning Center. The respondents demonstrated a notably high overall computed mean score of 4.37 in teaching competence, which corresponds to a verbal interpretation of "very competent." The demographic profile of teachers indicated that it did not significantly impact the teaching competence of the respondents. The majority of the learners successfully passed the competency-based examination. The demographic profile of learners, including factors such as sex, age, and civil status, showed no significant correlation with the outcomes of the competency-based examination. The distance of the residence from the Community Learning Center has been identified as a significant issue, as it poses one of the key challenges faced. Additional Community Learning Centers should be established to reach out to the others. Teacher's competence has no relationship with the learner's performance in the competency-based examination. To make the findings more justifiable and credible, the researcher is taking into consideration the possibility of involving a higher number of students and teachers in the study. This is due to the fact that the population sample poses a limitation. Several other students from the nearby provinces or regions ought to be included among the population of respondents.

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